

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE RESEARCH SOFTWARE & SYSTEMS

Insights from the First Research Software Indaba in Africa

Version 2 - 11 March 2025

Version 1 - 23 May 2023

Overview

Date	19 May 2023
Venue	V&A Waterfront, Cape Town, South Africa
Link	https://rse-indaba.org
Organisers	Talarify in partnership with ReSA and RSSE-Africa
Sponsor	Talarify
Report by	Anelda van der Walt & Noxolo Chalale
Report date	23 May 2023
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The Research Software Indaba aimed to bring together key stakeholders from the South African research software and systems ecosystem in a first-ever session dedicated to research software and systems:

- introducing the community to the global research software movement;
- discussing the state of research software and systems development in the country and more broadly on the continent;
- identifying opportunities for growing the local research software and systems community to share best practices, collaborate, and leverage opportunities.

About the Participants

Participating organisations

- Centre for High-Performance Computing (NICIS, CSIR)
- DIPLOMICS
- eLwazi Open Data Science Platform
- ICIPE/OpenScienceKE (Kenya)
- National Institute of Communicable Diseases
- North-West University IT: T&L and Research
- NRF-South African Environmental Observation Network
- Research Software Alliance
- RSSE-Africa
- Software Sustainability Institute
- South African Centre for Digital Language Resources
- South African National Bioinformatics Institute
- RSE @ Stellenbosch University
- Talarify
- The Carpentries
- University of Cape Town eResearch
- University of Cape Town ICTS
- University of Cape Town Scientific Computing Research Unit
- University of the Western Cape eResearch

Join the newly created mailing list to discuss and share local African research software and systems issues and resources!

JOIN NOW

RSS-related activities

Legend

Inhouse	Research software or systems (data/compute) development and/or maintenance for in-house research
Service	Research software or systems (data/compute) development and/or maintenance as a service to others
Funding	Provide funding for research software projects, infrastructure, research, training, etc
Training	Training in research software or infrastructure development, maintenance, etc.
Policies	Develop policies related to the research software ecosystem
Employer	Employ research software or infrastructure developers
Infrastructure	Provide access to specialised infrastructure on which research software runs (cloud/HPC)
Project management	Research software project management
Other	Other

* Data from Research Software Indaba participants

Challenges & Opportunities

- Network - connecting with stakeholders
- Funding - students, infrastructure,
- Staff - finding & retaining
- Skills
- Career definition and opportunities for RSSEs
- Lack of coordinated activity
- Sustainability
- Disciplinary silos
- Load shedding

- Growth of high-quality free/open-source software
- Professionalisation of software practices to create sustainable research software
- Building on progress made by international community over the years
- Growing numbers of experts in the country who can identify and address common problems and collaborate on solutions (omics, astronomy, NLP, etc.)
- Increased awareness of the importance of software through the open science drive
- Define metrics to capture the wealth of progress in the National system of innovation in South Africa

Indaba Resources

Topic	Speaker	Link to slides
An introduction to the global research software movement	Dr Simon Hettrick	https://bit.ly/3BOHNxB
RSE@SUN	Dr Kim Martin	Video: https://bit.ly/45swPeM Slides: https://bit.ly/3lwjVTp
The Research Software Alliance	Dr Michelle Barker	https://tinyurl.com/ReSA-indaba
The Carpentries	Dr Angelique Trusler	https://bit.ly/3OCTBe2
eLwazi: Open Data Science Platform for DS-I Africa	Dr Sumir Panji	https://bit.ly/3Mtk2Af

Insights into how long RSEs stay in a role based on the international RSE survey:

- “What is the expected duration (in years) of your current position (in total)?”
- “Where was your previous job based?” which allows you to see if the person was previously an RSE or not
 - [Current employment data](#)
 - [Previous employment data](#)

Useful links

Title	Link	Description
RSSE Africa	https://rsse.africa	The African research software and systems community. Join events, learn about local and international developments, resources, publications, and solutions. Share best practices and showcase African research software excellence. Discuss local contexts, challenges and opportunities and collaborate to find solutions.
ReSA	https://www.researchsoft.org/	A global organisation working to advance the research software ecosystem by collaborating with decision makers and key influencers.
Software Sustainability Institute	https://www.software.ac.uk/	The founder of the formal research software movement. An institution based in the UK that has shaped much of the work that has been happening in research software sustainability globally.
Society of Research Software Engineering	https://society-rse.org/	Originally the UK Research Software Engineers Association. Soc-RSE works to increase software skills across everyone in research, to promote collaboration between researchers and software experts, and to support the creation of an academic career path for Research Software Engineers. A UK-based community with global footprint.

More useful links

Title	Link	Description
Research software flyer	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7962748	A summary of the research software and systems landscape created for the African research software and systems community.
Relevant publications	https://www.researchsoft.org/	A collection of publications. Get in touch if you're looking for something specific. We can help you find it.
ADORE	https://zenodo.org/record/7740084	Draft of the Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability
RSE Slack workspace	https://forms.gle/eU6536gnRtyCVGyh9	Request access to the international RSE slack workspace and join #rsse-africa
RSSE Events	https://rsse.africa/events	Learn about opportunities. Share your events by emailing rsse-africa@talarify.co.za
Hidden REF	https://hidden-ref.org/	Celebrating all research outputs
RDA TIGER application for Working Group	https://bit.ly/rda-tiger	Proposal to develop a Working Group that will support research performing organisations worldwide to develop, align and implement policies on research software, as a key component of FAIR and open science.
CZI EOSS funding calls	https://bit.ly/czi-eoss	Grant programme from Chan Zuckerberg Initiative Open Science

Proposed actions

	Outcome	Lead	Due date	Status
1	Create mailing list. Invite Indaba participants as start	Anelda	23 May	
2	Update and share flyer	Anelda/Noxolo	23 May	
3	Share event resources	Anelda/Noxolo	24 May	
4	Write blog post	Anelda/Noxolo (everyone is welcome to write a post on their sites or repost the one we'll create)	26 May	
5	Share research software & systems funders' details to ensure they are invited to the Funders forum and planned event in Sept 2023 (in Montréal, Canada)	Anyone - please email kimberley.hartley@allianc.ecan.ca (funders forum liaison for ReSA) cc anelda@talarify.co.za	ASAP	
6	Provide feedback on the Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability .	Everyone (please circulate widely for more input by African researchers, funders, etc.)	DEADLINE 25 May	
7	Collaborate on paper for South African Journal of Science	Anelda/Alan/Peter can draft something for input by interested participants	Submitted March 2025 - preprint	
8	Submit proposal for 1-day research software focused event at annual CHPC conference	Kevin (CHPC) will notify the group when proposal submissions open	TBC	

 Done
 Unsure if anyone provided feedback
 Not yet done

Acknowledgements

Alan Christoffels (SANBI), Andiswa Msi (NWU IT: T&L and Research), Anelda van der Walt (Talarify), Angelique Trusler (The Carpentries), Caleb Kibet (ICIPE/OpenScienceKE, Kenya), Clement N Nyirenda (UWC eResearch), Devan Govender (UCT ICTS), Friedel Wolff (SADiLaR), Gloseije Bazolana (NICD), Kevin Colville (CHPC - NICIS, CSIR), Kevin Naidoo (UCT Scientific Computing Research Unit), Kim Martin (RSE @ SUN), Leo Chiloane (NRF-SAEON), Mattia Vaccari (UCT eResearch), Michelle Barker (ReSA), Noxolo Chalale (Talarify), Patricia Swart (DIPLOMICS), Peter van Heusden (SANBI, RSSE-Africa), Simon Hettrick (SSI), Sumir Panji (eLwazi ODSP)

Thank you to every participant who contributed to the discussions and plans for going forward! We look forward to continued collaborations and advancement in research software and systems on the continent.

Abbreviations

ADORE	Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability
CHPC	Center for High-Performance Computing (South Africa)
CSIR	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research
CZI	Chan Zuckerberg Initiative
DS-I	Data Science for Health Discovery and Innovation in Africa (NIH-funded)
Elwazi ODSP	Elwazi Ipen Data Science Platform
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSS	Essential Open Science Software
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
HPC	High-performance computing
ICIPE	International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (Kenya)
ICTS	Information and Communication Technology Services
IT	Information Technology
NICD	National Institute of Communicable Diseases (South Africa)
NICIS	National Integrated Cyberinfrastructure System (South Africa)
NIH	National Institute of Health (United States)
NRF	National Research Foundation (South Africa)
NWU	North-West University
RDA	Research Data Alliance
ReSA	Research Software Alliance
SADiLaR	South African Centre for Digital Language Resources
SAEON	South African Environmental Observation Network

Abbreviations

SANBI	South African National Bioinformatics Institute
Soc-RSE	Society of Research Software Engineering
SSI	Software Sustainability Institute (United Kingdom)
T&L	Teaching and learning
TIGER	Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
UCT	University of Cape Town
UK	United Kingdom
UWC	University of the Western Cape

Citation

Towards Sustainable Research Software & Systems: Insights from the First Research Software Indaba in Africa 2023 by Anelda van der Walt & Noxolo Chalale (Talarify). [V2 - 10.5281/zenodo.15006806](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006806) is licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)